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***N*-Aryl-*N*-acety lureido-*O*-alkylxanthates and Bis[*N*-aryl-*N*'-acety lureido]-*O*-polymethylene Bisanthates**

P. C. JOSHI, JR.*, K. B. KARNATAK, M. M. SAH

and

A. K. PANT

Chemical Laboratories, Kumaun University Campus, Almora-263 601

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A large number of salts of *O*-alkylxanthic acid have been reported to exhibit fungicidal activity^{1,2}. The benzyl ester of butylxanthate is used as insecticide for red spider³. Halogenopolynitro aryl esters of *O*-methyl- and *O*-ethylxanthic acid have been synthesised and screened for their fungicidal activity by Gupta *et al.*⁴. Chloroacetylcarbamides possessing insecticidal activities were described by Hoegberg *et al.*⁵. It was, therefore, considered of interest to condense chloroacetylcarbamides with potassium-*O*-alkylxanthates to obtain *N*-aryl-*N*'-acety lureido-*O*-alkylxanthates (1). In addition, chloroacetylcarbamides were also condensed with dipotassium-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates in the molar ratio 2 : 1 to yield bis[*N*-aryl-*N*'-acety lureido]-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates (2). All these compounds were screened for their antifungal activity.

TABLE 1—*N*-ARYL-*N*'-ACETY LUREIDO-*O*-ALKYLXANTHATES (1)^a

Compd no	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C
R' = OH,			
1	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	118
2 ^b	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	151
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	145-46
4.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	135
5	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	165-66
6.	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	145
7	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	146-47
R = C ₂ H ₅ ,			
8	H	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	124
9	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	213-14
10.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	152-53
11	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂	110
12.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	134
13.	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	144
14. ^c	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₃ S ₂	161

^aAll the compounds were obtained in 70-80% yield, and they gave satisfactory N, S analyses.

^b $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200 (NH), 1710 (NHCONH), 1592, 1500 (C=O, aromatic), 1400 (CH₂CO), 1245 (O-N, stretch), 1170 (C=S) and 765 (1,2-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, COOCH₂), 4.1 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7-7.5 (4H, m, ArH), 7.8 (1H, s, NHAr) and 10.2 (1H, s, CONHCO).

^c $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3210 (NH), 1700 (NHCONH), 1600, 1500 (C=O, aromatic), 1410 (CH₂CO), 1265 (O-N, stretch), 1190 (C=S) and 840 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 4 (2H, s, COOCH₂), 4.6 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.1-7.5 (5H, m, 4ArH+NH) and 10.35 (1H, s, CONHCO).

Potassium salts of xanthic acids were prepared from methanol, ethanol, ethanediol and propane-1,3-diol by their reaction with carbon disulphide and KOH⁷.

N-Aryl-*N*'-acety lureido-*O*-alkylxanthates (1) and bis[*N*-aryl-*N*'-acety lureido]-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates (2): A solution of potassium-*O*-alkylxanthate (0.02 mol) or dipotassium-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthate (0.01 mol) in 40 ml of acetone was

Experimental

Substituted phenylcarbamides and their corresponding chloroacetyl derivatives were prepared according to the methods reported earlier⁶.

added to a suspension of appropriate chloroacetyl-*N*-substituted phenylcarbamides (0.02 mol) in 50 ml of acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and then refluxed for 2 h. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The solid

* Rewati Niwas, Kholta Almora-263 601.

that separated out on cooling was filtered, washed several times with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol-water (Tables 1 and 2).

TABLE 2—BIS[*N*-ARYL-*N'*-ACETYLUREIDO]-*O*-POLY-METHYLENE BISXANTHATES (2)^a

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C
n=2			
15.	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	98-100
16.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	111
17.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	114
18.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	80-83
19.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	115-116
20. ^b	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	120
21.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	115
n=3			
22.	H	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	140-42
23.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	195-98
24. ^b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	189-90
25.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	205
26.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	160-61
27.	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	176-77
28.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	230-31

^aAll the compounds were obtained in 60-70% yield, and they gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

^b $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) Compd. 20, 3210 (NH), 1700 (NHCONH), 1600, 1492 (C=C, aromatic), 1405 (CH₂CO), 1240 (O-N, stretch), 1130 (C=S) and 835 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹; Compd. 24, 3200 (NH), 1700 (NHCONH), 1600, 1520 (C=C, aromatic), 1415 (CH₂CO), 1245 (O-N, stretch), 1180 (O=S) and 810 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹.

Screening for antifungal activity: All these *N*-aryl-*N'*-acetylureido-*O*-alkylxanthates (1) and bis[*N*-aryl-*N'*-acetylureido]-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates (2) were screened for their antifungal activity against *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Alternaria alternata* as the test fungi by paper-disc plate method of Thornberry⁸ at concentrations 2.0 and 0.2% (w/v). Standard PDA medium was used. Filter paper discs of diameter 12 mm were used and the diameter of zones of inhibition formed around each disc after incubating for a period of 48 h at 25-28° were recorded. Results were compared with the reference fungicide, Thiram 75W. The compounds 1, 3, 4, 5, 9, 15, 18, 20, 21, 22, 26 and 27 were found to possess significant antifungal activity against all the test fungi.

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Synthesis of Substituted Acetamides as Potential Antibacterial and Antiviral Agents

ANIL K. SENGUPTA, ASHOK K. PANDEY

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007 and

H. N. VERMA and M. M. A. A. KHAN

Plant Virus Laboratory, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

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1,2,4-TRIAZENES are associated with diverse pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial^{1,2}, antiviral³, antiinflammatory⁴, antimalarial⁵, insecticidal⁶ and AchE inhibitory activities⁷ and in addition, aryl ureas have also been reported to exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities. With this view it was thought of interest to synthesise various 2-[[8-substituted-5H/CH₃-1,2,4-triazeno[5,6-b]indol-3yl]-thio]-*N*-[[substituted phenyl]amino]-carbonyl]-acetamides (5-26) by condensing 8-substituted-5H/CH₃-1,2,4-triazeno [5,6-b]indol-3-thiol (1-4) and chloroacetylated ureas in ethanolic NaOH solution.

Scheme

Experimental

The structures of all the compounds were checked by ir recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord